

THE USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: The use of technology has become an important part of the learning process in and out of the class. Every language class usually uses some form of technology. Technology has been used to mutually help and progress language learning. Technology enables teachers to adapt classroom activities, thus enhancing the language learning process. Technology continues to grow in importance as a tool to help teachers facilitate language learning for their learners. This learning focuses on the role of using new technologies in learning English as a second/foreign language. It discussed different approaches which support English language learners to increase their learning skills through using technologies. In this article, the scholar defined the term technology and technology integration, explained the use of technology in language classroom, reviewed previous studies on using technologies in improving language learning skills, and stated certain recommendations for the better use of these technologies, which assist learners in improving their learning skills.

Keywords: technology, language learning, use

The use of modern technology in teaching English is broadly understood to include an innovative application of methods, tools, materials, devices, systems, and strategies which are directly relevant to English language teaching and lead to the achievement of the desired goals. Thus, while technology is now generally accepted as an imperative educational and supporting tool across a range of teaching and learning contexts, it is particularly true of English language teaching since it affords a number of potential prospects to enhance both the content and delivery of the pedagogies typically associated with traditional English language instruction. This is primarily achieved by enabling the student and/or teacher to revisit problematic content time after time until it is fully understood and assimilated. Familiarity with the concept of using modern technology is not simply limited to the use of modern appliances and devices, but rather achieves to the introduction of innovative systems and methods of teaching which facilitate faster and more comprehensive learning progression. According to prevailing pedagogical theories, in utilizing the learning potential of technology students are better able to acquire and hone their language knowledge and skills. The use of technology in teaching English consolidates the integrated view of the modern means system and association with other components which benefits students by achieving the required results. The use of modern technology in English language teaching has therefore become indispensable, especially in the wake of unprecedented developments crosswise numerous fields and disciplines. It is essential that the teaching sector keep apace of the global technological revolution by adopting modern technological means such as computerization, multi-media devices, mobile phones, audio/visual effects applications, and social media, to optimize English language instruction and equip teachers to connect with classroom language learners in a systematic and advanced way. The Internet provides easy, immediate, and virtually unlimited

access to software, applications, and a host of ancillary platforms and materials which can expedite English education and learning. While these affordances may be widely available to all, it is noted that teachers often play a fundamental role in operating the dissimilar tools and teaching methods. Additionally, many such programmes are definitely designed to promote effective English teaching whilst concurrently increasing learner appreciative and achievement of English language skill.

The issue of English language teaching and learning has emerged as one of the central issues of current educational debate as studies have consistently demonstrated poor standards of student achievement across all levels. Since the current era is epitomized by the global use of technology, it follows that technology has entered the field of teaching on a worldwide measure. In fact, since most educational institutions have now absorbed such technology into existing and future curricula, technological and/or media-based pedagogies have assumed considerable prominence due to proven enhanced learning outcomes, especially in comparison with traditional teaching methods. Obsolete teaching practices include a n

- 1) Traditional methods lead students through precise curriculum content and rely on outdated learning aids such as blackboards and textbooks. As such, the teacher merely relays the information without accounting for positive or negative results.
- 2) Traditional methods rely on simple strategies that do not meet the purpose of learning or basic needs in the process of teaching. Since such teacher-centred pedagogies situate the learner as a recipient, their overarching goal is the extent to which a student can replicate information without necessarily understanding it.
- 3) Students rely on received sounds and images as opposed to interaction and discussion with the teacher.
- 4) Student accreditation by means of set texts tend to foster boredom and loss of motivation and attention in attainment, as opposed to modern technological teaching methods which inhere numerous incentives that increase the likelihood of acquiring English language skills in a timely and positive way. In light of the above obstacles, the present study was undertaken to ring-fence the causes at the heart of the problem and attempt to resolve the issue by introducing a range of modern technologies into the context of English language teaching number of problems, as follows:

- 1) Traditional methods main students through precise curriculum content and rely on invalid learning aids such as blackboards and textbooks. As such, the teacher merely relays the information without accounting for positive or negative effects.
- 2) Traditional methods rely on simple strategies that do not meet the purpose of learning or basic needs in the process of teaching. Since such teacher-centred pedagogies position the learner as a recipient, their principal goal is the extent to which a student can imitate evidence without necessarily understanding it.

- 3) Students rely on received sounds and images as opposed to communication and argument with the teacher.

- 4) Student qualification by resources of set texts tend to foster boredom and loss of motivation and attention in attainment, as conflicting to modern technological teaching methods which inhere numerous incentives that increase the likelihood of obtaining English language abilities in a timely and positive way. In light of the overhead obstacles, the present study was accepted

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The student followed each of the following methodologies:

1) The scholar useful the descriptive method and experimental monitoring in order to fully cross-examine the study questions and devise appropriate solutions.

2) Recognized on the determination of time and spatial period, the application of historical methodology based on an analysis of the elements and reasons which gave rise to the basic research problem and the attendant challenges supplementary assisted an evaluation of present and future developmental impacts. Additionally the collation, review and comparison of secondary data sourced from relevant records, reports and previous studies, were intrinsic to the design and scope of effective solutions.

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Conclusion. In summary, it is clear that despite unaffected efforts to modernize traditional methods of teaching English, residual obsolete practices should be phased out and replaced by the use of the available technology on proposal using computer, smart devices, display, audio-visual materials, and electronic approaches. This study underscores the vital educative potential and numerous benefits of technology in the language classroom for positive learning outcomes in the language classroom and the wider world, the financial implications of setting up the infrastructure, and encouraging teachers to overcome their concerns around of teaching technologies. Certainly, the purpose of both traditional and modern technologies is to maximize students' English skills and provide a space where learning can be best facilitated. One of the ultimate goals of using modern technology is to actively engage them students in language learning and motivate them to acquire English language skills in a practical and realistic way. This can be achieved through an open learning context which fosters openness and access to the subjects and information through modern technology means, wherein students are motivated and directed to communicate with each other. In terms of future development, it is clear that multimedia will be integral to the student-centred process of teaching English to modern standards. As such, the quality of teaching and application of students to modern

educational foundations would benefit from an extensive survey of English language skills in to improve overall communication proficiency. In conclusion, we believe that this process can fully enrich student thinking and practical language skills and promote improved usefulness in overall teaching and learning. Indeed it is evident that many routine learning issues that can be overcome through the effective incorporation of technology and appropriately trained teachers, while funding ramifications can be addressed complete ministerial planning and the establishment of an infrastructure which prioritizes the interests of effective learning.

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